

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF "TECHNOLOGICAL DETERMINISM" IN THE TEACHING OF TECHNICAL SCIENCES

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1. Introduction

Today, in-depth teaching of concepts of high scientific importance to students of technical educational institutions and development of their competence and worldview on this basis remains one of the urgent tasks. In this regard, the role of the concept of technological determinism in the development of professional knowledge and skills of technical education students is high. In our country, on the basis of changes in the higher education system, educational reforms aimed at in-depth teaching of scientific concepts and increasing the theoretical knowledge and scientific outlook of future personnel are being carried out.

Technological Determinism (TD)

Figure 1. Stages of applying the effectiveness of improving knowledge about the concept of technological determinism in educational processes.

Because as a result of technical and technological innovations, inventions and improvements, they serve not for human well-being, but for the decline of civilization, which worries mankind. Directing technology and technological development to social stability on the basis of technological determinism is one of the urgent tasks [1]. Therefore, the formation of knowledge and outlook on the concept of technological determinism among future technical specialists as creators of techniques and technologies, artificial intelligence, is gaining priority. In this regard, a lot of work is being done within the framework of the state policy. In particular, "strategy and mechanisms of innovative development of our country are closely related to the effective use of the intellectual and scientific-technical potential created in this country.

2. Improving students' knowledge of the concept of technological determinism

To deepen the content of technical education to students in higher technical education institutions, at the same time to explain the approaches to the perspectives of technical education, in particular, to teach approaches within the concept of technological determinism and technostatic determinism, through which technical and technological It is important to link development to the chains of cause and effect in society, to understand technological progress through the combination of cause and effect, to improve the methodology of teaching the system of views in this regard [2]. In this sense, in-depth teaching of technological concepts in technical education students, influencing their understanding of the laws of technological development, in particular, the essence of the concept of technological determinism, its place in technical education, the division of technical education the impact of requirements on professional maturity and the analysis of their possibilities in developing a technical and technological

worldview is a priority. The following table shows that the effectiveness of improving knowledge about the concept of technological determinism is also important in the processes of automation and design of technological processes.

3. Conclusion

The current state of innovative socio-economic indicators directly depends on the activities of qualified personnel with high potential, high spirituality and moral culture. Also, innovative development appears as a factor that unites the cooperation of state and non-state organizations. This process, in turn, leads to the strengthening of the human factor in the innovative activity of a person, it is embodied as an important factor in the increase of his social status and the improvement of the living conditions of the population. Achieving innovative development and regular improvement of the national education system strengthens the confidence of the population, especially young people, in the future. Such a process, in turn, requires young people and future specialists to pay special attention to the factors that ensure innovative activity. It is important to analyze and generalize the results obtained in the process of developing knowledge about the basics of the concept of technological determinism among students of technical higher education institutions, and to develop a methodology for determining the level of efficiency.

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